

An Overview of the Most Important Medicinal Plants Native to Iran by Property of Burn Wound Healing: A Systematic Review

Mehrdad Karimi¹, Mahnaz Mardani², Leila Mahmoodnia^{3*}

¹Department of Surgery, Shahrekord University of Medical Sciences, Shahrekord, Iran

²Nutritional Health Research Center, Health and Nutrition Department, Lorestan University of Medical Sciences, Khorramabad, Iran

³Department of Internal Medicine, Shahrekord University of Medical Sciences, Shahrekord, Iran

Available Online: 25th April, 2017

ABSTRACT

Burn is an injury where the skin is destroyed by various factors such as heat, cold, electricity, etc. When skin injury occurs, pathogens can invade the body and burn wounds get infected shortly after the damage. The wound healing process is a process done by the coordination of tissues, cells and various factors. In the acute phase, inflammatory mechanism of burns has negative effects due to capillary leak. On the other hand, in the later stages of burn, inflammation is necessary for wound healing. Silver nitrate, silver sulfadiazine, and Mafenide acetate are also used for wound care. These compounds cause delayed wound healing and have cytotoxic effects. Iran is among the countries that have rich traditional medicine and herbal treatment of burn wounds in history. Therefore, in this review article, we tried to report the medicinal plants native to Iran which are effective for burn wounds. In this review article, by searching databases such as Scopus, Google Scholar, Spy DVD, mag Iran and... the articles were searched by searching keywords including burn wounds, herbs, extracts, essences and Iran. After finally searching, it was determined that medicinal plants below are the most important medicinal plants native to Iran that affect burn wounds. 11 Medicinal herbs 11 Abukhalsa plant, chamomile, oak, hungry for love, green tea, purslane, cinnamon, Hypericum, and Commiphora are the most important Medicinal Plants which are effective for burn wound healing in Iran. Alkanin, Naphthoquinone and Shikonin, tannins, pectin, alkaloids, saponins and tannins fixed, resin and vitamin C, flavonoids rutin, aucubin and catalpol Catechin, Epicatechin, Epicatechin Gallate, Epigallocatechin and Epigallocatechin-gallate, oxalic acid, Cinnamic acid, caffeic acid, maleic acid, Citric acid, coumarin, flavonoids, alanine, tannins, alpha-linolenic acid, cinnamic acid, phenolic compounds such as eugenol, and safrolephellandrene, terpene compounds such as limonene and linalool, trans-cinnamaldehyde (MDA), tannins, coumarin, resin, Cinema-hydroxy phenyl propane compounds such as formaldehyde and mannitol, curcumin, terpenoids, steroids, Flavonoids, lignans are active compounds of plant bioactive substances that are effective on burn wound healing.

Keywords: medicinal plants, healing, burns, Iran.

INTRODUCTION

The skin is responsible for multiple tasks such as maintaining skin hydration, preventing the penetration of pathogenic agents into the body, and protecting the underlying structures. Therefore, any disruption in its integrity can be considered severe harm to the body. Still one of the main causes of death and disability in many countries are thermal injuries and burns. 1200000 people are burned annually in the United States that require treatment¹. In addition to the physical and psychological consequences of severe burns due to needing multiple surgeries and the rehabilitation, it's widely considered to be the most costly of diseases². Burn injuries are traumatic events that are associated with systemic and local effects¹. Burns are injuries where the skin by various factors such as heat, cold, electricity, etc. is destroyed. When the skin is injured, pathogens can invade the body and burn wounds get infected shortly after the

damage is done³⁻⁵. Burn wounds are divided into various types based on the cause. A variety of burn wounds including chemical, electrical, and radiation burns are divided. Another type of categories of burn wounds include first-degree burns which includes the involvement of epidermis. Second degree burns, which in addition to epidermis, also involves dermis and third-degree burns destroy all layers of the skin¹. Burn wounds are good places for starting an infection. Thus, wound infection repeatedly occurred in these patients and is considered one of the most important causes of their deaths⁴. In the meantime, the wound healing is a process that occurs when the tissues, cells and various factors are coordinating with each other. In the acute phase of burn, inflammatory mechanism has negative effects due to capillary leakage. On the other hand burns in the later stages of inflammation is necessary for wound healing⁶. Silver nitrate, Mafenide acetate, and silver sulfadiazine

Table 1: Medicinal plants native to Iran of burn wounds with scientific name, family and supplemental information.

Row	Scientific Name	Family Name	Persian Name	Description
1	<i>Arnebiaeuchroma</i>	Boraginaceae	Abukhalsa	Abukhalsa 1% and 10% effect on wound healing mice second-degree burn ²⁰
2	<i>Matricariachamomilla</i> L	Asteraceae	Chamomile	Topical application of chamomile extract 20%,causes improvement in the second degree burns in two lab rats ¹⁴
3	<i>Quercusbrantti</i>	Fagaceae	Oak	Results of a study in male Wistar rats indicated that the thickness of the epidermis and the dermis of the skin and reduction of burn rate in receiving groups of aqueous extract of oak had 1, 4 and 7% and silver sulfadiazine compared with the control group increased significantly ²¹
4	<i>Aloysia citrodora</i>	Verbenaceae	Quince	The results of an experimental study in BALB/c mice showed that the percentage of burn wound healing in the 21 st day in grain groups was 99.502, silver sulfadiazine group 92.26, the Vaseline group 97.69 and 92.97 for the control group ²²
5	<i>Scrophulariastrata</i>	Scrophulariaceae	Scrophularia	Results of a study in Wistar rats showed that 2.5% dose of the Scrophularia plant has a significant effect in the treatment of burn wounds ²³
6	<i>Camellia sinensis</i>	Theaceae	Green Tea	Results of a study in male Wistar rats showed no healing time and burn for containing or lack of ointment extract and respectively were 0.62 ± 18 and 0.38 ± 20.33 ²⁴
7	<i>PortulacaOleracea</i> L	Portulacaceae	Purslane	Results showed a 10% dose of Purslane extract accelerates the healing of burn wounds in BALB / c mice ²⁵
8	<i>Cinnamomumzeylanicum</i>	Lauraceae	Cinnamon	Cinnamon extract accelerates the burn wound healing in male Wistar rats ²⁶
9	<i>Hypericum perforatum</i>	Hypericaceae	Hypericum	Results of a study in male Wistar rats showed that Hypericum reduces the average surface burns, epidermal thickness and the malondialdehyde ²⁷
10	<i>Commiphoramyrrrha</i>	Bursaceae	Commiphora	2.5 percent of the Commiphora plant extract had a well healing process on burn wound healing in rats ²⁸
11	<i>Myrtus communis</i>	Myrtaceae	Myrtle	Ethanol extract of Myrtle increase the number of blood vessels, and fibroblasts at the site of the burn on the skin of male mice rats ²⁹

are also used for wound care². Silver sulfadiazine compounds are used as the main treatment for burns. These compounds cause delayed wound healing and are cytotoxic effects^{7,8}. Thus, attempts to find natural ingredients that affect the burn is in progress. According to these, several studies in different fields such as biotechnology, pharmacognosy, medicinal chemistry and etc have paid special attention to medicinal plants to find new drugs effective in the treatment of burn wounds. The use of plants, plant extracts and other herbal preparations to treat of various diseases⁹⁻¹⁹, cuts, wounds and burns in many countries have a long history. In countries such as India and China, where traditional medicine has a long history and is powerful, there are valuable information on the many unknown plants and forests in the treatment of wounds. Iran is among the

countries that have a rich history in traditional medicine and herbal treatment of burn wounds. Therefore, in this review article medicinal plants that are native to Iran which are effective in healing burn wounds are reported.

METHODS

In this review, articles were searched by searching the databases of Scopus, Google Scholar, Magiran, etc and searching keywords including burn wounds, herbs, extracts, essences and Iran.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

After searching finally found that 11 plant Abukhalsa herbs, chamomile, oak, hungry for love, green tea, purslane, cinnamon, Hypericum, Commiphora and wounds of the most effective herbs are native to Iran.

Additional information about the medicinal plants native to Iran of burn wounds can be seen in Table 1. Based on the results, Abukhalsa plants, chamomile, oak, hungry for love, green tea, purslane, cinnamon, Hypericum, Commiphora and wounds of the most effective herbs are native to Iran. In traditional medicine the Abukhalsa plant is an antiseptic and wound healing plant³⁰. The root of the Abukhalsa plant contains Alkaline, Naphthoquinone, and Shikonin³¹. In traditional medicine, chamomile is used for pityriasis, eczema, acne and bronchial treatment quality for coughs and colds, and acts as a fever redactor³². The most important chemical in the Oak plant is Tannin³³. In traditional medicine Quince is used for hoarseness, laryngitis, inflammation of the bronchi and especially for washing burn wounds³⁴. In the Quince grain there are amounts of Pectin, alkaloids, saponins and fixed tannins, resin and Vita min C, Flavonoids rutin³⁵. Scrophularia is used for the treatment of gastrointestinal diseases, infectious diseases, pulmonary, wound cleaning and healing of fever³⁶. Scrophularia contains compounds of aucubin and catalpol^{37,38}. Green tea contains compounds such as Catechin, Epicatechin, EpicatechinGallate, Epigallocatechin and is Epigallocatechin-gallate³⁹. Active ingredients Purslane contains oxalic acid, Kynamyk acid, caffeic acid, maleic acid, citric acid, coumarin, flavonoids, alanine, tannins, alpha-linolenic acid and is Glucosoids of menotropin⁴⁰. Cinnamic acid, phenolic compounds such as eugenol, and safrolephellandrene, terpene compounds such as limonene and linalool, trans-cinnamaldehyde (MDA), tannins, coumarin, resins, compounds such as hydroxy phenyl propane Cinema (MDA) and mannitol are the most important ingredients of cinnamon extract⁴¹. The most important compound of the turmeric plant is curcumin⁴². Phytochemistry studies on the plant indicate the presence of terpenoids, steroids, Flavouids, and lignans⁴³. Find effective drug combinations for the treatment of any disease is a scientific strategy for control, prevention and treatment of disorders⁴⁴⁻⁴⁸. It seems that the effective compounds in the named plants for burn wound healing are made up of effective bioactive substances.

REFERENCES

- Forjuoh SN. Burns in low- and middle-income countries: a review of available literature on descriptive epidemiology, risk factors, treatment, and prevention. *Burns*. 2006; 32(5): 529-37.
- Holmes JH, Heimbach DM. Burns. In: Brunnicardi FC, Andersen DK, Billiar TR, Dunn DL, Hunter JG, Pollock RE. *Schwartz's principles of surgery*. 8th ed. NewYork: McGraw- Hill; 2005; 204-28.
- Unkhwan H, Shouguang I. Expression of the soxR gene of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* is inducible during infection of burn wounds in mice and is required to cause efficient bacteria. *Infect and Immun*. 1999; 67(10): 5324-31.
- Miri MR, Hemmati H, Shahraki S. Comparison of efficacy of honey versus silver sulfadiazine and acetate mafenid in the treatment of contaminated burn wounds in piggies. *Pak J Med Sci*. 2005; 21(2): 168-73.
- Dale K MR, Schnell G, Wong PJ. Therapeutic efficacy of "Nubiotics" against burn wound infection by *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. *Antimicrob Agents Chemother*. 2004; 48 (8): 2918-23.
- Evers LH, Bhavsar D, Mailander P. The biology of burn injury. *ExpDermatol*. 2010; 19(9): 777-83.
- Atiyeh BS, Costagliola M, Hayek SN, Dibo SA. Effect of silver on burn wound infection control and healing: review of the literature. *Burns*. 2007; 33(2): 139-48.
- Dai T, Huang YY, Sharma SK, Hashmi JT, Kurup DB, Hamblin MR. Topical antimicrobials for burn wound infections. *Recent Pat Antiinfect Drug Discov*. 2010; 5(2): 124-51.
- Bahmani M, Tajeddini P, Ezatpour B, Rafieian-Kopaei M, Naghdi N, Asadi-Samani M. Ethenobotanical study of medicinal plants against parasites detected in Shiraz, southern part of Iran. *Der Pharmacia Lettre*. 2016;8(1):153-60.
- Samarghandian S, Asadi-Samani M, Farkhondeh T, Bahmani M. Assessment the effect of saffron ethanolic extract (*Crocus sativus* L.) on oxidative damages in aged male rat liver. *Der Pharmacia Lettre*. 2016;8(3):283-90.
- Jivad N, Asadi-Samani M, Moradi MT. The most important medicinal plants effective on migraine: A review of ethnobotanical studies in Iran. *Der Pharmacia Chemica*. 2016;8(2):462-6.
- Parsaei P, Bahmani M, Karimi M, Naghdi N, Asadi-Samani M, Rafieian-Kopaei M. A review of analgesic medicinal plants in Iran. *Der Pharmacia Lettre*. 2016;8(2):43-51.
- Jivad N, Bahmani M, Asadi-Samani M. A review of the most important medicinal plants effective on wound healing on ethnobotany evidence of Iran. *Der Pharmacia Lettre*. 2016;8(2):353-7.
- Rouhi-Boroujeni H, Asadi-Samani M, Moradi MT. A review of the medicinal plants effective on headache based on the ethnobotanical documents of Iran. *Der Pharmacia Lettre*. 2016;8(3):37-42. 8
- Parsaei P, Bahmani M, Naghdi N, Asadi-Samani M, Rafieian-Kopaei M. The most important medicinal plants effective on constipation by the ethnobotanical documents in Iran: A review. *Der Pharmacia Lettre*. 2016;8(2):188-94.
- Asadi-Samani M, Kooti W, Aslani E, Shirzad H. A Systematic Review of Iran's Medicinal Plants with Anticancer Effects. *Journal of Evidence-Based Complementary and Alternative Medicine*. 2016;21(2):143-53.
- Bahmani, M., Sarrafchi, A., Shirzad, H., Rafieian-Kopaei, M. Autism: Pathophysiology and promising herbal remedies. *Current Pharmaceutical Design* 2016; 22(3): 277-285.
- Ebrahimie, M., Bahmani, M., Shirzad, H., Rafieian-Kopaei, M., Saki, K. A Review Study on the Effect of Iranian Herbal Medicines on Opioid Withdrawal Syndrome. *Journal of Evidence-Based*

- Complementary and Alternative Medicine 2015; 20(4): 302-309.
19. Bahmani, M., Shirzad, H., Rafieian, S., Rafieian-Kopaei, M. Silybum marianum: Beyond Hepatoprotection. Journal of Evidence-Based Complementary and Alternative Medicine 2015; 20(4): 29: 292-301.
 20. Hoseini-Tahmasbi M, Hoseini-Tahmasbi S, Karamidehkordi A, Delaram M, MalekAnzabi J, Fatahi F. Effect of Arnebiaeuchroma root extract on burn wound healing in Balb/c mice. J ShahrekordUniv Med Sci) 2013; 15(4): 54-61.
 21. Nikrooze L, JafariBarmak M, Naghmachi M, Ghafarianshirazi H, Dehghani N. Study of Jaft Aqueous Extract and Silver Sulfadiazine on Burn Healing in Male Rat. Armaghane-danesh, Yasuj University of Medical Sciences Journal 2013; 18(2): 74: 107-114.
 22. Tajoddini A, Rafieian-kopaei M, Namjoo AR, Sedehi M, Ansari R, Shahinfard N. Effect of Ethanolic Extract of Cydonia Oblonga Seed on the Healing of Second-Degree Burn Wounds. Armaghane-danesh, Yasuj University of Medical Sciences Journal 2011. 17(6): 72: 494-501.
 23. Azhdari-Zarmehri H, Nazemi S, Ghasemi E, et al. Assessment of effect of hydro-alcoholic extract of scrophulariastrata on burn healing in rat. J BabolUniv Med Sci 2014;16(5):42-48.
 24. Asadi S.Y., A. Zamiri, S. Ezzati1, P. Parsaei, M. Rafieian, H. Shirzad. Effect of alcoholic extract of green tea (Camellia sinensis) on the healing process in surgical and burn wounds in rats. BirjanUni Med Sci J 2011;18(1): 1-9.
 25. Rafiee-Vardanjani L, Sahinfard N, Rahimi –Madiseh M, Ansari -Samani R, Rahimi M, Parvin N, Taji-Eshkaftaki F. [Effect of Portulacaoleracea L vs. silver sulfadiazine on burn wound healing in Balb/C mice. J SharekordUniv Med Sci. 2012; 13(6): 92-100.
 26. Delfan B, Bahmani M, Eftekhari Z, Jelodari M, Saki K, Mohammadi T. Effective herbs on the wound and skin disorders: A ethnobotanical study in Lorestan province, west of Iran. Asian Pacific Journal of Tropical Disease 2014; 4(S2): 938-942.
 27. Momeni E, Aroi N, Aroi M, JafariBarmak M, Mahmoudi R, Malekzadeh JM, et al. The Effect of HypericumPerforatum Extract and 1 % Silver Sulfadiazine on Second Degree Burn Wound Healing in Male Rats. Armaghane-danesh 2014; 19(7): 625-632.
 28. Yadeghar, O, Asghari, A, Hesaraki, S. Evaluation of wound healing activity of Commiphoramyrtha extract compared with silver sulfadiazine on experimental skin burn healing in rat. Journal of Veterinary Clinical Pathology 2013; 7(27): 173-182.
 29. Jorsaraei GHS, Moghadamnia AA, Firouzjahi AR, Miri SM, Omranirad A, Saghaei R, Hashemi SF. A campirason on histopathological effects of Myrtus extract and silver sulfadiazine 1% healing on second degree burn wound in rats. Qazvin Uni Med Sci J 2006; 10(1): 1-11.
 30. Amin G. Motedaveltaringiahanedaruyeisonnati Iran. 2nd ed. Tehran: Tehran University of Medical Sciences; 2008.
 31. Sharma RA, Singh B, Singh D, Chandrawat P. Ethnomedicinal, pharmacological properties and chemistry of some medicinal plants of Boraginaceae in India. J Med Plant Res. 2009; 3(13): 153-75.
 32. Segal R, Pilote L. Warfarin interaction with Matricariachamomilla. CMAJ. 2006; 174(9):1281-2.
 33. Visuthikosol V, Chowchuen B, Sukwanarat Y, Sriurairatana S, Boonpucknavig V. Effect of aloe vera gel to healing of burn wound a clinical and histologic study. J Med Assoc Thai 1995; 78(8): 403-9.
 34. Saneie S. LagharBashid. Tehran: Entesharate Hafez Novin;1997;204.
 35. Mehrin M. Khavasegiahanedaruee. Tehran: EntesharateKhashayar; 2002;188.
 36. Mozafarian VA. Khuzastan flora: Agriculture natural resources research. 1st ed. Ahvaz: Publication Center of Khuzestan Province 1999; p: 353.
 37. Park SU, Park N, Kim YK, Suh SY, Eom SH, Lee SY. Application of plant biotechnology in the medicinal plant RehmanniaglutinosaLiboschitz. J Med Plants Res 2009;3(13):1258-63.
 38. Recio MC, Giner RM, Manez S, Rios JL. Structural considerations on the iridoids as anti-inflammatory agents. Planta Med 1994;60(3):232-4.
 39. Kim H, Kawazoe T, Han DW, Matsumara K, Suzuki S, Tsutsumi S, et al. Enhanced wound healing by anepigallocatechin gallate-incorporated collagen sponge in diabetic mice. Wound Repair Regan 2008; 16(5): 714-720.
 40. Mizutani M, Hashidoko Y, Tahara S. Factors responsible for inhibiting the motility of zoospores of the phytopathogenic fungus Aphanomycesochlioides isolated from the non-host plant Portulacaoleracea. FEBS Lett. 1998 Nov; 438(3): 236-40.
 41. Dashti-Rahmatabadi MH, VahidiMerjardi AR, Pilavaran AA, Farzan F. Antinociceptive effect of cinnamon extract on formalin induced pain in rat. ShahidSadoughi University of Medical Sciences 2009; 17: 190-99.
 42. Mesa MD, Ramirez – Tortosa MC, Aguilera CM, Ramirez- Bosca AY GIL A. Pharmacological and nutritional effects of Curcuma Longa extracts and curcuminoids. ArsPharmaceutica. 2000; 41(3): 307-21.
 43. Su, S., Wang, T., Duan, J.A., Zhou, W., Hua, Y.Q., Tang, Y.P., et al.(2011). Anti-inflammatory and analgesic activity of different extracts of Commiphoramyrtha. Journal of Ethnopharmacology, 134: 251-258.
 44. Ilkhanizadeh B, Mehrshad A, Seddighnia A , Zarei L. Comparison between effects of free and niosomal formulations of Artemisia annua L. (asteraceae) on chronic myelogenous leukemia (K562) cell line. International Journal of Pharmacology 2017; 13(2): 191-197.
 45. Behroozi-Lak T, Zarei L, Moloody-Tapeh M, Farhad N, Mohammadi R. Protective effects of

- intraperitoneal administration of nimodipine on ischemia-reperfusion injury in ovaries: Histological and biochemical assessments in a rat model. *Journal of Pediatric Surgery* June 05, 2016.
46. Zarghani, S.S., Soraya, H., Zarei, L., Alizadeh, M. Comparison of three different diet-induced non alcoholic fatty liver disease protocols in rats: A pilot study. *Pharmaceutical Sciences* 2016; 22(1): 9-15.
47. Bakhtiary Z. Shahrooz R, Ahmadi A, Zarei L. Protective effects of ethyl pyruvate on sperm quality in cyclophosphamide treated mice. *Iranian Journal of Reproductive Medicine* 2015; 291-296.
48. Delfan B, Bahmani M, Eftekhari Z, Jelodari M, Saki K, Mohammadi T. Effective herbs on the wound and skin disorders: A ethnobotanical study in Lorestan province, west of Iran. *Asian Pacific Journal of Tropical Disease* 2014; 4(S2): 938-942.